

Communication Skills Improving Assistance

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ABSTRACT

Virtual Reality (VR) is a computer technology that generates realistic images, sounds and other sensations that simulate a user's physical presence in a virtual or imaginary environment. The proposed system nurtures personal traits of an individual which plays a major role in every sector. The system helps to improve an individual's social, personal, and language skills as well as cures phobia of standing in front of audience. With advancement in technology, we are developing a system on Unreal Engine for creation of various environments as well as 3ds Max for creating Virtual Objects which are been placed. The learner is supposed to be in an environment where he/she is been judged while appearing for various rounds. Further, video is captured and uploaded on the system and trainers does the evaluation. Trainers are supposed to suggest area of improvement by commenting on the parameters defined. Regular usage of software enhances skills of the user. The proposed system is a VR based (verbal/non-verbal) interactive system for enhancing communication skills based on predefined and planned of greeting scenario. Results in each stage are compared and analyzed to get the clear idea of where the person is lacking. The outcome of this practice test leads to improvement in individual's personality, difficulties raised in each environment results in upgradation of selfdom.

Keywords: *Virtual Reality, Simulated World, Unreal Engine, 3ds Max, Communication Skills*

1. Introduction

This section describes the term Virtual Reality and introduces the concept of Virtual Reality Technology. It also gives the overview of the system which describes the deliverables of the project.

1.1 Overview

Virtual Reality is a computer technology that generates realistic images, sounds and other sensations that simulate a user's physical presence in a virtual environment. The proposed system allows a person to face a situation where he/she must speak staying in a simulated world with no fear. This type of immersive learning in the can provide learners a real opportunity to learn by doing, thereby increasing motivation and retention.

2. Literature Survey

Despite recent technological advances that make VR systems more appealing to Clinical practice, there is still a considerable lack of scientific evidence of how VR systems can be meaningfully implemented in existing rehabilitation routines. A number of recent reviews have been published on the use of VR and video games for physical rehabilitation. The reviewed studies conclude that VR technology allows therapy to be provided within a functional, purposeful and motivating context V-Buddy is an audio-based application, is designed to provide a solution to overcome students' lack of confidence to speak in Virtual World. This interdisciplinary study Integrates ICT in education through the innovation of an interactive audio-based application as a tool to enhance

English language speaking skills among less proficient Students. Drawing on the socio cultural perspective of learning, the application named 'V-Buddy' has been developed and tested with a group of participants which consists of five primary school students and an English language teacher. Adopting one group pre-test and post-test experimental design as its methodology, the teacher was asked to evaluate the students' level of confidence to speak prior to and after their engagement with the V-Buddy. Cambly gives instant access to native English speakers over video chat. Complete training is given by professional trainers through a video call. Cambly is an online tutoring platform that connects English learners in more than 130 countries with native speakers. Cambly offers English language tutoring services 24/7. The company inactively seeking dynamic, engaging and patient Native English speakers from around the world to work for them as online tutors. When you talk to a student or paying Cambly user, you get paid to speak conversationally with the student and provide any help that is needed by the student while you both are online. If you are a native English speaker, this should be pretty easy. Unreal Engine 4 is a suite of integrated tools for game developers to design and build games, simulations, and visualizations. One virtual reality games was researched and developed, based on Unreal engine 4 and the HTC Vive. Some key technologies was used in this game, such as path finding through algorithm or waypoints, particle system, file access and other technologies, combined with 3D sound effect and UI editor, etc. Autodesk 3ds Max is a professional 3D computer graphics program for making 3D

Fig. 6.1 Class Diagram

7. Implementation Details

7.1 Android Application

Basic steps we followed to create Android Application for VR technology are:

- 1. Asset creation:** First we modelled all the 3d objects required in the environment. For that, we used Autodesk 3dsMax. After modelling 3d objects, we applied textures on those objects.
- 2. Environment creation:** Then we created an environment in Unreal Engine 4. We applied proper lighting on it to give a realistic look. Here we import the entire asset which is required to place in an environment such as tables, chairs, characters, etc. and placed it in a proper position.
- 3. Enable plug-in:** As we have to develop application for cardboard VR, we enabled Google VR plug-in before packaging the project.
- 4. Setup for packaging:** We applied all the required project setting for a controller, input, default game mode, default level, etc. We also created a main menu widget.
- 5. Packaging:** Then we start packaging the project for android platform.

7.2 Web Application

As the system functions to evaluate video of student performed in particular environment. So web application provides platform for trainer and student to register themselves and upload the video and evaluate respectively. The application generates result which is viewed by student and also comments if any by the trainer.

8. Technical Specifications

8.1 Advantages

1. Improves communication of people on the basis of regular evaluation and reduces chances of Jargons while speaking.
2. User will be self-confident to present himself/herself.
3. Overcomes phobia of speaking in front of bulk of people.
4. Creates Interest in person to learn.
5. Evaluation will be done easily on the basis of specified criteria like language Fluency, content of speech, gestures, eye contact, speech delivery, voice tone, etc.

8.2 Limitations

1. Limited for Extempore situation (Other situations like Group Discussion, HR Interviews, etc. are not supported).

8.3 Applications

1. It provides a virtual environment in which students can safely practice real-world skills.
2. Helps in distance learning.

8.4 Hardware and Software Requirement

8.4.1 Hardware Requirement

Hardware and software requirements for the system are stated below:

1. Google cardboard for virtual experience.
2. Computer system with Webcam and internet connection.
3. Android smartphone with Gyro sensor.

8.4.2 Software Requirements

Unreal engine4

Autodesk 3ds max

Wamp Server

9. Conclusion

We are developing a VR based (verbal/non-verbal) interactive system for developing communication skills based on predefined and planned of greeting scenario. Our project consists of 2 modules. First module is for Evaluation and second module is for Realistic Environment. To create realistic environment, we are using Unreal Engine 4, Because it supports photo-realistic environments. We are using Autodesk 3ds Max for modelling 3d objects. It is easy to use than other software's like Autodesk Maya or Blender or Cinema 4D. The system provides various environments based on levels which are been faced by the users. The result of practice test will lead to improvement of speaking in front of audience as well as development of individual's personality. Difficulties raised in each environment will result in up-gradation of selfdom.

10. Reference

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